

**DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHER OF
PRESCHOOL EDUCATION ORGANIZATIONS**

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Abstract: Further improvement of the system of preschool education in our country, strengthening the material and technical base, expanding the network of preschool educational institutions, providing qualified teaching staff, a radical increase in the level of preparation of children for schooling, ways of education and upbringing, the use of modern educational programs in this process and technologies.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his speech at an expanded meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers on the main results of the socio-economic development of our country in 2016 and the most important priorities of the economic program for 2017: The first urgent task is the development of preschool education, stressed that this is how it should be.

Therefore, competence is "how a specialist behaves in non-standard situations, unexpected situations, enters into communication, stands in a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses conflicting information, consistently develops and" possession of an action plan in complex processes . "

Professional competence is the acquisition by a specialist of the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for professional activities, and their practical application at a high level.

The formation of professional competence among future teachers is a requirement of time and a social necessity.

Important pedagogical conditions for the preparation of a future teacher can be recognized as:

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Important pedagogical conditions for the preparation of a future teacher can be recognized as:

- regulatory and educational and methodological documents that meet modern requirements (state educational standard, model curricula, working curricula, model curricula, work programs, textbooks, educational availability of teaching aids, methodological recommendations, additional specialized literature, teaching aids, lesson plans, projects, etc.);
- a high level of knowledge, skills and qualifications of scientific and pedagogical staff (professors, associate professors, teachers, qualified teachers, technical staff), a sufficiently developed level of professional competence and scientific potential;
- material and technical support of the educational process (educational buildings, classrooms, training workshops, practical laboratory equipment), information technology (radio, television, computer, copying equipment, laboratory equipment, audio system, availability of a set of video, multimedia, simulators), film projectors, slide projectors, video projectors, technical equipment, etc.) are available in sufficient quantity;
- creation of a favorable social and educational and technological environment (content, focus, unity of purpose, etc. relationships between teachers, students, leaders and students, as well as students);

Consi stent, continuous and systematic implementation of organizational and educational and practical activities.

Today, in preparing children for school education, the task of raising them to think independently is one of the main goals. The solution to this problem depends to a

large extent on the use of interactive teaching methods. First of all, let's clarify the concept of "interactive". The word "interactive" comes from the English word "interact". "Inter" means mutual, "act" means to work. Such methods are aimed at involving everyone in the audience, requiring collaborative work. The essence of interactive teaching is to organize the educational process in such a way that all students are involved in the learning process and have the opportunity to think freely, analyze and think logically.

The development of society is manifested in the content of profession and professional culture and essence. Professional culture is manifested in labor activities. Indicators and results of mastering this part of culture are the production, use, and maintenance of professional competence, professional activity: reading, improving the skills of using knowledge and devices: specialization skills: organizational competence - issues of professional activity to provide oneself with information, to coordinate one's actions with colleagues in joint activities, to be self-directed in decision-making, independence, to the final result focused self-examination, professional and ethical appearance in the establishment of business relations with officials, handling of employment documents, handling of the workplace and tools, understanding of best practice, innovative processes, modern technologies and In conclusion, the process of covering each subject and topic, focusing on the formation of high-level knowledge and professional competence of the students, will help them to become high-potential and competitive personnel in the future. First of all, this serves as the main factor for the development of society. After all, the training of highly qualified pedagogues first of all ensures that young people with potential will grow from the place of education and training in the future. Summarizing the definitions and descriptions given to the concept of "professional competence of a pedagogue", it can be interpreted as follows: Professional competence of a pedagogue is one of the important aspects of professional competence in the activity of a pedagogue, and all the needs of a pedagogue related

to the implementation of only profession and professional activity, represents abilities, skills, knowledge and interests.

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